

Cation- π interaction in metalloproteins : A bioinformatics approach

P. Anitha, R. G. Swetha, Anand Anbarasu and Sudha Ramaiah*

Bioinformatics Division, School of BioSciences and Technology,
VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : sudhaanand@vit.ac.in

Abstract : Cation- π interaction plays an important role in protein structure stability. In our present study, we have analyzed influence of cation- π interaction in structural stability of metalloproteins. We observed that cation- π interactions of Arg/Lys- π interactions might have a significant role in the global conformational stability of metalloproteins. Though Trp residues have lower natural occurrence (1.76%) in proteins but it's shown the higher energetic contribution in metalloproteins. The preference of Arg interactions with Tyr and Trp is higher. Arg/Lys- π interactions in metalloproteins will be useful for further structural studies and functional involvement on these proteins.

Keywords : Metalloproteins, cation residues, π interactions, sequential distance.

Introduction

Metalloproteins play a vital role namely enzymes, signal transduction, transport and storage proteins and almost half of the proteins need metals to perform their functions¹. These have been attractive targets in the field of protein design and engineering². The weak attractive forces are important in determining the three dimensional structure of proteins³. Especially, cation- π interactions have an important role in the stability of protein structures⁴. Numerous studies stating the value of Arg/Lys interactions with π residues and it's recognized to be essential non-covalent links in structural biology⁵⁻⁷.

Experimental

Dataset :

We extracted 35 (non-redundant) X-ray resolved structures out of 1096 structures from Protein Data Bank. These are chosen based on the selection criteria⁷. These are listed in Table 1.

CaPTURE (Cation Pi Trends Using Realistic Electrostatics) :

By using CaPTURE, an energetically significant interaction (interaction energy ≤ 2 kcal/mol) among metalloproteins complexes was preferred for further bioinformatics analysis⁸.

Secondary structure preferences :

Dictionary of protein secondary structure (DSSP) is preformed to identify the secondary structure preferences such as H (helix), T (turn) and S (strand) for interacting Arg/Lys- π residues⁹.

Solvent accessibility patterns :

The systematic analysis was performed for Arg and Lys residues involved in interactions with π residues in metalloproteins using DSSP. Solvent accessibility describes the physical representation of water molecules in direct contact with the protein or with a particular part of the protein with geometrical representation⁹.

Stabilization centers :

We preformed stabilization centers for our dataset to screen distinct amino acids which might be responsible for the prevention of the decay in the folded protein structure¹⁰.

Sequence conservation :

The conservation scores were categories into nine grades. Grade one includes the most variable positions; grade five indicates the intermediately conserved positions and grade nine denotes the most conserved positions^{11,12}.

Sequence separation between residues involved in Arg/Lys- π interactions :

The comparison of the surrounding residue was ana-

lyzed for our dataset, in terms of the location at the sequence level. The ranges includes $< \pm 4$ (short-range contacts), $> \pm 4$ to $< \pm 20$ (medium-range contacts) and $> \pm 20$ (long range contacts)^{13,14}.

Results and discussion

Arg and Lys interactions with pi residues :

The dataset of our study includes 10451 amino acid residues and 145 energetically significant Arg/Lys-pi interactions which are taken from PDB (Protein Data Bank). These are depicted in Table 1. The percentages of Arg/Lys-pi interacting pairs in metalloproteins are Arg-Trp

Table 1. The percentage of occurrence of cation and pi residues in metalloproteins

PDB ID	%R/K	%F	%Y	%W
1AWD_A	5.4	2.1	5.3	0.0
1B0L_A	12.9	4.3	3	1.4
1D4A_A	12.1	6.2	3.7	2.2
1DLM_A	8.4	3.6	4.2	0.6
1DXQ_A	11.4	5.9	3.7	2.2
1HFX_A	10.5	2.4	4.1	2.4
1LNH_A	11.4	4.4	3.7	1.8
1OI8_A	11.2	3.4	4.0	1.3
1P9R_A	13.3	2.5	1.1	0.0
1RRH_A	11.3	4.4	3.6	1.8
1UNF_X	10.7	5.6	4.2	3.7
1VEW_A	11.2	5.4	3.4	2.9
1WZD_A	11.5	4.3	3.8	1.0
1XM5_A	4.6	2.6	2.6	1.3
1Y67_A	8.8	3.8	4.3	2.9
1YGE_A	10.2	3.6	4.4	1.7
1Z6R_A	8.0	2.1	2.1	0.5
2AFM_A	7.8	4.6	3.7	2.2
2CF4_A	10.1	4.4	3.5	0.9
2DD5_C	12.1	2.9	3.9	2.7
2E46_A	8.3	3.2	1.9	0.0
2IF6_A	13.8	3.6	5	2.8
2IQ6_A	4.8	3.4	4.4	1.7
2IVN_A	12.7	4.0	3.4	0.3
2NXF_A	9.3	4.2	3.5	1.6
2P18_A	9.2	5.7	4.2	0.4
2RDV_A	7.7	3.8	5.8	1.9
2VW7_A	9.4	3.3	3.3	1.5
2Z68_A	11.5	4.3	3.8	1.0
2ZOW_A	9.2	2.6	0.7	0.0
3D19_A	13.1	7.7	1.9	0.8

Table-1 (contd.)

3EXM_A	11.9	2.9	1.4	8.1
3FW1_A	9.6	6.1	3.5	2.6
3HIP_A	8.6	2.5	1.2	3.7
3PCG_M	9.7	4.6	3.5	1.6
Mean	10.05	4.01	3.42	1.76

R - Arginine; K - Lysine; F - Phenylalanine; Y - Tyrosine; W - Tryptophan.

(27%), Arg-Phe (24%), Arg-Tyr (16%), Lys-Trp (13%), Lys-Tyr (11%) and Lys-Phe (9%). The results indicate that an energetically significant cation-pi interaction with Trp residues is higher in metalloproteins. The energetic contribution from Arg-Trp is higher and Lys-Tyr is minimal. The average Arg/Lys interaction energy with pi residues is around -4.67 kcal/mol. From our results, we suggest that Trp residues and Arg-Trp pairs might play a significant role in the structural stability of metalloproteins. The Arg-pi interacting pairs in lactoferrin [PDB ID 1B0L_A] are represented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Interaction between Arg with Phe, Tyr and Trp in Lactoferrin (PDB ID 1B0L_A).

Secondary structure preferences :

The preference of Arg/Lys-pi interaction shows that the Arg interactions with Tyr and Trp predominantly stabilize the helices. Whereas, Lys interactions with Phe prefer to be in coils and sheets. Our results suggest that the stabilization patterns of the secondary structures are independent of amino acid class in metalloproteins.

Solvent accessibility patterns :

Our results of solvent accessibility patterns indicate

that the majority of Arg and Lys residues are in the solvent exposed regions and majority of pi residues prefer to be in the buried regions. We imply that these interactions might stabilize the interface between the core and terminus in metalloproteins.

Stabilization centers :

Our result of stabilization centers revealed that the percentages of Arg/Lys-pi interacting residues with located stabilization centers in metalloproteins are Lys (34%), Trp (31%), Arg (30%), Tyr (26%) and Phe (23%). We assume that the Arg/Lys-pi interacting residues might provide more stability to metalloproteins.

Sequence conservation :

The proportions of Arg/Lys-pi interacting residues is classified based on conservation scores six (cut off) which includes Trp (65%), Tyr (65%), Arg (55%), Phe (44%) and Lys (43%). From our results, we found the majorities of the residues in Arg/Lys-pi interactions are evolutionarily conserved and might play important role in stability of metalloproteins.

Sequence separation between residues involved in cation-pi interaction :

Sequence separation results indicated that the majority of the Arg/Lys-pi interacting pairs are found to be in long-range contacts. Therefore, these Arg/Lys-pi interactions might have significant contribute in the stability of the native structure of the protein molecule. This may also involve in retaining the best conformation of those proteins while binding with the metals.

Metal binding sites :

The results state the amino acids concerned in metal binding are not involved in Arg/Lys-pi interactions. However, a small number of metal binding pockets are stabilized by Arg/Lys-pi interactions. Thus, we could not locate amino acids in metal binding pockets in most structures. We suggest that Arg/Lys interactions with pi residues may not contribute to functional specificity.

Conclusion

Our bioinformatics investigation on Arg/Lys-pi interactions in metalloproteins created a strong case to believe that these interactions to be considered important in structural studies.

Acknowledgement

Dr. Anand Anbarasu gratefully acknowledges the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), Government of India agent for the research grant IRIS ID : 2011-03260. We thank the Management of Vellore Institute of Technology University for offering the required facilities for completing this research work.

References

1. L. Rulisek and J. Vondrasek, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1998, **71**, 115.
2. C. Sousa, A. Cebolla and V. de Lorenzo, *Nature Biotech.*, 1996, **14**, 1017.
3. P. D. Barker, *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.*, 2003, **13**, 490.
4. A. Anbarasu, S. Anand, M. M. Babu and R. Sethumadhavan, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, 2007, **40**, 479.
5. O. Takahashi, Y. Kohno and M. Nishio, *Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **110**, 6049.
6. D. A. Dougherty, *Science*, 1996, **271**, 163.
7. H. M. Berman, J. Westbrook, Z. Feng, G. Gilliland, T. N. Bhat, H. Weissig, I. N. Shindyalov and P. E. Bourne, *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 2000, **28**, 235.
8. J. P. Gallivan and D. A. Dougherty, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1999, **96**, 9459.
9. W. Kabsch and C. Sander, *Biopolymers*, 1983, **22**, 2577.
10. Z. Dosztányi, A. Fiser and I. Simon, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1997, **272**, 597.
11. F. Glaser, T. Pupko, I. Paz, R. E. Bell, D. Bechor-Shental, E. Martz and N. Ben-Tal, *Bioinformatics*, 2003, **19**, 163.
12. M. Landau, I. Mayrose, Y. Rosenberg, F. Glaser, E. Martz, T. Pupko and N. Ben-Tal, *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 2005, **33**, 299.
13. M. M. Gromiha and S. Selvaraj, *J. Biol. Phys.*, 1997, **23**, 151.
14. M. M. Gromiha, C. Santhosh and S. Ahmad, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, 2004, **34**, 203.